

PsyNLP: A Multi-Modal NLP System for Privacy-Preserving Mental Health Text Analysis

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Abstract

Mental health disorders remain a critical global issue, yet the widespread adoption of digital screening tools is hindered by user distrust and privacy concerns associated with third-party cloud-based text processing. To address this, we introduce **PsyNLP**, a privacy-preserving framework designed for fully local execution on consumer hardware. PsyNLP implements a hybrid multi-modal pipeline including lightweight transformer models (BERT, DeBERTa) for rapid emotion and category classification with quantized Large Language Models (LLMs) for high level context-aware severity assessment and reasoning. We evaluate the system’s architecture, safety guardrails, and computational performance, discussing the trade-offs between on-device resource constraints and analytical depth. This work serves as a proof-of-concept for accessible, decentralized mental health screening that prioritizes data protection with the utility of modern NLP techniques.

Keywords

Natural Language Processing, Mental Health, BERT, LLM, Privacy-Preserving, Text Analysis, Emotion Detection

1 Introduction

Mental health disorders, such as depression, are among the leading causes of disability worldwide [8]. According to the World Health Organization’s *Mental Health Atlas 2020*, with a global median of only 13 mental health workers per 100,000 people and service coverage for severe conditions as low as 29%, the traditional healthcare model is struggling to keep pace with demand [9]. Early identification and tracking through daily writing (e.g., journals, notes, posts) can facilitate timely support, yet many digital tools depend on cloud processing and non-transparent data collection practices, creating trust and privacy barriers for mental illness screening and reaching for help. Meanwhile, recent advances in transformer models and efficient local AI runtimes make on-device analysis feasible without exporting sensitive text [1–3].

This article introduces **PsyNLP**, a privacy-preserving, locally-deployed text analysis system for mental health signals. PsyNLP combines lightweight transformer classifiers with an on-device LLM to assess emotions, infer mental health categories, and synthesize user- or clinician-oriented reports.

The contributions of this project are:

- **Multi-model pipeline:** Integrates BERT-based emotion detection [5] with a custom trained DeBERTa-based mental health classification [10] and an LLM [11] [7] for contextual severity assessment.

- **Privacy-first:** Runs fully on-device via llama.cpp runtime and transformer pipelines [2][5][10], avoiding cloud APIs and reducing data exposure risk.
- **Dual-mode reporting:** Generates summaries and suggestions for both general users (with self-help recommendations) and professional users (with clinical insights).

2 System Architecture

2.1 Overview

PsyNLP follows a modular pipeline architecture as illustrated in Figure 1. The system processes input documents through four main stages: preprocessing, NLP classification, LLM analysis, and report generation.

Figure 1: System Architecture of PsyNLP

2.2 NLP Classification Module

The classification module (`predict_nlp.py`) employs two specialized transformer models:

2.2.1 Emotion Detection. We utilize a fine-tuned BERT model (`boltuix/bert-emotion`)[5] for multi-class emotion classification. The model identifies emotions including: *sadness, anger, love, surprise, fear, happiness, neutral, disgust, shame, guilt, confusion, desire, and sarcasm.*

2.2.2 Mental Health Classification. A DeBERTa model (`elishaw/deberta_mental`)[10] classifies text into mental health categories with associated severity scores:

Table 1: Mental Health Categories and Severity Scores

Category	Severity Score
Normal	0
Stress	2
Anxiety	4
Depression	6
Bipolar	7
Personality Disorder	8
Suicidal	10

2.3 LLM Severity Assessment Module

The LLM module (`predict_llm.py`) serves as a context-aware classifier designed to validate and refine the severity assessment. Unlike traditional statistical classifiers, the LLM component leverages semantic understanding to distinguish between genuine distress and casual usage of emotional language.

2.3.1 Preprocessing and Sanitization. To prevent model hallucinations caused by formatting artifacts, the system implements a rigorous cleaning pipeline (`remove_markdown_artifacts`). This includes stripping Markdown syntax, code blocks, and non-semantic symbols before the text reaches the inference engine. This step is crucial for maintaining classification stability across different writing styles (e.g., Reddit posts vs. plain text journals).

2.3.2 Prompt Engineering. We utilize a role-playing system prompt that defines seven distinct severity levels (Normal to Suicidal). For models supporting "Chain of Thought" (CoT), such as Qwen-3, we inject a specific instruction: *"Think step-by-step: first analyze the emotional content, then determine severity."* This forces the model to generate internal reasoning traces before outputting the final classification label, significantly improving zero-shot accuracy.

2.3.3 Hybrid Safety Guardrails. A raw LLM prediction is not treated as final. To mitigate false positives—especially for the critical "Suicidal" category—we implemented a rule-based post-processing layer (`adjust_classification`):

- (1) **First-Person Intent Verification:** The system checks for the co-occurrence of self-referential pronouns (e.g., "I", "my") and intent verbs (e.g., "want", "plan") using the `indicates_personal_intent` function. This distinguishes actionable threats (e.g., "I want to end it") from abstract discussions (e.g., "Suicide is a tragedy").

- (2) **Length Heuristics:** Extremely short segments (< 3 words) classified as high-risk are automatically downgraded to "Normal" to prevent context-less false alarms.
- (3) **Keyword Validation:** If the LLM predicts "Suicidal" but no high-risk keywords are present, the label is downgraded to "Depression" or "Stress" based on secondary keyword matches.

2.3.4 Dynamic Model Loading. To ensure accessibility on consumer hardware, the system dynamically selects the inference engine based on available RAM:

- < 6 GB RAM: Loads Gemma-3 1B (Q4_0 quantization), prioritizing speed and low memory footprint.
- ≥ 6 GB RAM: Loads Qwen-3 4B Thinking (IQ4_XS quantization), prioritizing deeper reasoning capabilities.

2.3.5 Keywords for Severity Analysis. Large language models (LLMs) possess strong zero-shot capabilities and in-context understanding. However, LLMs are prone to **hallucinations** during tasks[6], especially when utilizing models with fewer parameters. Therefore, we introduce high-risk keywords to trigger enhanced scrutiny:

Listing 1: Risk keyword detection

```

1 SUICIDAL_KEYWORDS = {
2     "suicide", "kill_myself",
3     "end_my_life", "want_to_die",
4     "self-harm", "no_reason_to_live"
5 }
```

2.4 Severity Score Calculation

The overall severity score combines NLP and LLM predictions using a weighted formula:

$$S_{overall} = 0.3 \times (S_{psy} \times C_{psy}) + 0.7 \times S_{avg} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- S_{psy} : DeBERTa psychological severity score
- C_{psy} : DeBERTa confidence score
- S_{avg} : Average LLM severity across sentences

3 Experiments and Evaluation

3.1 Hardware and Environmental Setup

We evaluated the performance of PsyNLP across two distinct hardware environments to simulate MPS accelerated inference and edge computing scenarios:

- **Environment A (Kaggle CPU):** Intel Xeon @2.20 GHz (4 vCPUs/ 31.35 GB RAM). Represents edge computing with low CPU availability.
- **Environment B (MPS):** Apple MacBook Pro (M1 Max, 32 GB RAM, macOS 26.1). High-performance workstation using Metal Performance Shaders (MPS).

3.2 Performance Benchmarking

We measured the execution time for two core functions: `calculate_text_severity()` (individual text analysis) and `calculate_article_severity()` (batch processing of longer documents).

Figure 2: PsyNLP Inference Latency (Individual Text)

Figure 3: Relative Speedup of MPS over CPU

4 Ethical considerations

4.1 Data and Privacy

PsyNLP is explicitly designed to minimize data exposure risk. All inferences runs locally on user devices, and no connections with third-party servers. The system does not store raw documents, user can delete reports from the reports folder. By prioritizing on-device computation, PsyNLP seeks to mitigate surveillance concerns associated with commercial mental-health screening AI tools.

4.2 Misjudgment Risk and Responsibility Boundaries

Although local AI models are advancing rapidly, hallucinations in large language models remain a persistent issue. Even though PsyNLP is a carefully designed screening tool, it cannot replace human experts in clinical diagnosis. Misclassifications, particularly

false positives or false negatives in high-risk categories, can lead to unnecessary anxiety and delay access to professional care, and therefore results should always be interpreted cautiously.

4.3 Suicide and Crisis Management

PsyNLP does not provide specific advice beyond grounding strategies and resource suggestions. Instead, the system directs users toward crisis-support services (such as 988 in the United States).

5 Discussion

5.1 Performance

5.1.1 Latency and Throughput. The latency for individual text inference in both environments is displayed in Figure 2. PsyNLP significantly reduces latency when compared to the Kaggle CPU baseline on MPS-enabled (or other GPU/TPU accelerations) hardware, especially for models that depend on transformer attention. The benefit of specialized matrix-acceleration hardware is reflected in this improvement, which becomes more noticeable as input length increases. When compared to CPU execution, MPS typically reduces end-to-end inference latency by 86–89%, resulting in a speedup of 7–9x.

5.1.2 Hardware Preference. Overall, PsyNLP is optimized for edge devices. But we still recommend at least 8 GB of RAM for deployment to ensure stable model performance. Increasing the number of CPU cores generally improves performance, because different documents and batch segments can be processed in parallel.

When available, hardware accelerators such as GPUs, TPUs, or Apple’s MPS provide substantially greater benefit. As shown in our experiments, offloading transformer inference to MPS yields a 7–9x speedup, reducing latency by nearly 90%. This makes real-time or near-real-time screening feasible for short documents. Therefore, while PsyNLP remains usable on CPU-only machines, deployment on devices with dedicated acceleration offers the best balance between privacy, responsiveness, and user experience.

5.2 Limitations

Although PsyNLP demonstrates that privacy-preserving mental-health screening is technically feasible on consumer hardware, the system has several limitations.

First, PsyNLP models are trained on publicly accessible dataset[4], which is dominated by English speakers and Western internet culture (primarily from Reddit), are the source of biases that PsyNLP inherits. As a result, common non-Western emotional expression patterns could be misunderstood.

Second, the models operate only on textual signals. Psychological assessment in clinical practice typically combines interviews, longitudinal observation, and multimodal information such as behavior, speech patterns, and clinical history. As a result, PsyNLP may miss relevant context or misinterpret figurative or culturally-specific expressions.

Third, the current workflow still needs to be optimized. Currently, PsyNLP relies on a loose coupling pipeline that invokes independent NLP and LLM processing sequentially. A more efficient architecture should merge shareable steps (such as tokenization, text standardization, and caching of intermediate representations)

and introduce asynchronous task scheduling, allowing sentence-level LLM reasoning to be executed in parallel with document-level Transformer classification.

Fourth, our analysis at the system-architecture level remains limited. While PsyNLP demonstrates that privacy-preserving psychological inference is feasible on consumer hardware, the current study focuses primarily on implementation rather than systematic architectural reasoning and high reliability. At this stage, our evaluation is still insufficient to conclusively show that PsyNLP attains deployment-grade accuracy for psychological text classification and analysis. Future research will need controlled comparisons against predetermined baselines and thorough validation across bigger, more varied datasets, such as clinically annotated datasets.

6 Conclusion

By combining lightweight transformer classifiers with an on-device LLM, PsyNLP demonstrates that privacy-preserving mental-health text analysis is possible on consumer hardware. The system reduces data-exposure risk while maintaining practical latency by enabling preliminary screening without storing sensitive content to external servers through a hybrid severity assessment. However, there are still a number of unresolved issues, such as robustness under real-world usage conditions, large-scale validation, and architecture-level reasoning. Therefore, rather than being a clinical diagnostic tool, PsyNLP should be considered an exploratory proof-of-concept. In order to assess safety and efficacy in realworld scenarios, future work will focus on larger expert annotated datasets, bolstering architectural rigor, fine-tuned LLM models, and working with psychology specialists.

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